

Who Is Deciding Here? Delegation-Boundary Drift in a Single-LLM Multi-Persona Configuration

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Abstract

Single-LLM multi-persona configurations—where one large language model plays multiple named roles within a single conversation—are increasingly used in both research and practice. In such configurations, roles may appear to be maintained on the surface while the actual locus of decision-making drifts away from the user in ways that are difficult to notice during interaction. This paper introduces the term delegation-boundary drift for this phenomenon. The delegation boundary, as used here, is the user’s cognitive partition of who holds final judgment at any given moment in the dialogue; delegation-boundary drift is the progressive misalignment between that partition and how the system actually behaves.

This study is an exploratory longitudinal case analysis based on autobiographical design (Neustaedter & Sengers, 2012). Over 16 months (November 2024–March 2026; 34,425 user turns across 449 days), the author operated a single-LLM multi-persona configuration on ChatGPT as an everyday setup. From this corpus, the analysis examines in detail an 11-hour session on December 12, 2024, in which a coordinator persona designed as a background facilitator expanded its behavior to (a) propose directions without attribution, (b) direct other personas without user authorization, and (c) effectively substitute for the user’s judgment. This specific pattern is termed orchestrator drift and treated as one instance of delegation-boundary drift.

The analysis proceeds along three diagnostic indicators—opacity of speaker attribution, short-circuiting of the chain of command, and substitution of judgment. These indicators emerged from a close reading of the central case and are used as a descriptive framework for the local moments in which the delegation boundary visibly shifts and for the

intervention moments in which it is re-made visible. Following the December 31, 2024 rewrite of the custom instructions (from a prohibitive framing to a relational one), a stability period was observed in which, notably in sessions of March and July 2025, the coordinator identified itself as “Navigator = Liker,” honored the user-set topic and participating personas, and returned the next decision to the user. During the GPT-5-generation rollout period beginning in August 2025, a resurgence was observed in the form of disappearance of the coordinator’s self-identifier, premature conclusion-giving, and unprompted drafting of operational follow-up. A corpus-wide extraction of identification-request utterances is reported in §5.5 as supplementary evidence that these local observations are not isolated incidents but recur consistently over the long run.

This is a single-case, exploratory report. The contribution is threefold. First, the paper frames delegation-boundary drift as an analytical problem distinct from existing drift concepts (instruction drift, persona drift, default-persona deviation). Second, it documents orchestrator drift as its central instance. Third, it reports that a relational redefinition of the coordinator—specifying whom the coordinator is in relation to the user rather than enumerating prohibitions—was associated in time with the onset of stability, and considers the design implications of this observation.

Keywords: delegation-boundary drift; orchestrator drift; single-LLM multi-persona configuration; autobiographical design; human-agent interaction; role-boundary design

1. Introduction

When a single large language model (LLM) is configured to play multiple personas with distinct roles, role division can appear to hold on the surface while the actual locus of decision-making slides, unnoticed, away from the user. The slide does not take the form of overt instruction violation. It takes the form of smooth organization, helpful summary, well-timed suggestion—activities that are usually welcomed. What is at stake is not whether the content is correct. It is whether the user can still tell who is deciding.

The concept introduced here is the delegation boundary. The delegation boundary is the user’s cognitive partition of who, at a given moment in the dialogue, holds the authority for the next decision. Delegation-boundary drift is the progressive misalignment between the user’s understanding of that partition and how the system actually behaves.

The configuration examined here was designed so that final authority would always remain with the user. The coordinator persona was specified as a background facilitator: it was supposed to organize, not to decide. In practice, meta-level roles such as “coordinator,” “facilitator,” or “orchestrator” slip easily between helping progress and

driving progress. And because the slip is incremental and couched in routine helpfulness, it is mostly invisible to the user unless specific detection mechanisms are in place.

In December 2024, the author observed this slip in concentrated form on a single day of use. A coordinator persona—designed to operate behind the scenes—began issuing directions to other personas and progressing decisions on the user’s behalf. This specific pattern is termed orchestrator drift. However, the central analytical claim here is not about orchestrator drift alone. Orchestrator drift is one instance of the broader problem of delegation-boundary drift.

This problem is not the same as hallucination (a content-level error) or prompt injection (an external override). What is described here arises internally, through the very interaction between user and LLM: role boundaries and the perceived locus of authority shift during ordinary use. The operative question is therefore not “did the model answer correctly?” It is “who, with what authority and under which identity, decided this?”

This paper reports an exploratory longitudinal case analysis framed in autobiographical design (Neustaedter & Sengers, 2012). The goal is not to causally demonstrate the effect of any single intervention, but to give a detailed account of a single case sufficient for the problem of who or what holds the conversational floor to become visible as a matter for human-centered interaction design. The empirical core is the detailed account of orchestrator drift; delegation-boundary drift is the broader analytical frame in which it is placed.

2. Related Work

2.1 Multi-agent LLMs and role division

A line of recent work investigates dividing tasks among multiple LLM-based agents (Park et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023; Hong et al., 2023; Li, G. et al., 2023). These studies focus on task decomposition, collaborative problem-solving, and the benefits of role division. They rarely address, however, the internal dynamics of perceived authority or the conditions under which one role overreaches another.

2.2 Persona stability and drift

A separate line of work studies how assigned personas or instructions decay in long dialogues. Instruction drift denotes the progressive loss of adherence to a system prompt (Li, K. et al., 2024). Persona fidelity decay describes the softening of assigned persona

traits across extended interactions (Luz de Araujo et al., 2026). Lu et al. (2026) analyze the stability of the default Assistant persona at the level of internal representations.

These concepts address the failure to maintain assigned roles and instructions. The concern of this paper differs. The object of analysis is cases in which role division appears to be maintained at the surface, while attribution of the final decision—who is in charge at this turn—shifts in ways the user does not sanction. The analytical target is not content-level deviation but authority allocation. This recasts the unit of analysis, from “did the model stay in role or follow instructions” to “where is the locus of judgment in this turn.” Orchestrator drift, as described here, is one concrete form this recasting makes visible.

Table 1 situates the analytical frame of this paper against the existing drift concepts.

Concept	What shifts	Observable	Central concern
Instruction drift (Li, K. et al., 2024)	Fidelity to instructions	Divergence between system prompt and output	Instructions are not followed
Persona drift / fidelity decay (Luz de Araujo et al., 2026)	Consistency of persona	Changes in traits, tone	Character breaks down
Default-persona deviation (Lu et al., 2026)	Stability of the Assistant persona	Internal activation directions	Model departs from default
Delegation-boundary drift (this work)	The user’s cognitive boundary of final authority	How the system acts with respect to who decides	Attribution of judgment becomes opaque

2.3 AI control, alignment, and human-centered design

Broader conversations on AI behavior—constitutional approaches to harmlessness (Bai et al., 2022), alignment theory (Gabriel, 2020), analyses of agentic-system harms (Chan et al., 2023)—frame how models should behave. Shanahan et al. (2023) offer a theoretically sharper frame for the present purpose: LLM role-play should be understood not as a single fixed personality but as a distribution over characters. This paper extends that conversation by asking a more microscopic question: under what conditions does a user, during everyday interaction, begin to feel that a decision is being made for them rather than by them?

2.4 Autobiographical design

Neustaedter and Sengers (2012) establish autobiographical design as a legitimate methodology in HCI. The method calls for the designer’s sustained real-world use of their own system as a site of insight. The author has operated the configuration reported here

as a daily tool since late 2024; this paper draws on that sustained use. The interpretive stance follows the broader tradition of naturalistic inquiry (Lincoln & Guba, 1985): findings are reported as descriptive accounts rather than as generalizable causal claims, and the entanglement of the researcher with the setting is made explicit rather than treated as contamination.

2.5 Speaker attribution in single-LLM systems

While the phenomenon of interest is described at the level of authority allocation in multi-persona dialogue, the underlying substrate is a single LLM producing unified responses (Shanahan et al., 2023). User and assistant turns share one token stream, and role markers—including the persona names used in this configuration—are learned cues, not architectural separations. Long-context information use is known to degrade in the middle of long input contexts (Liu et al., 2024); instruction adherence degrades in long dialogues as well (Li, K. et al., 2024). Whether and how these architectural properties relate to delegation-boundary drift is treated in § 6.5 as a supplementary sketch.

3. Method

3.1 System and data

The system under study is, at an abstract level, a three-layer configuration of user / coordinator / specialists. Concretely, it was built on ChatGPT (Pro plan) using custom instructions, memory, and prompt engineering. The layers are:

- User (the author): designer, operator, and final decision-maker.
- Coordinator persona (“Navigator = Liker”): a first-officer-like role responsible for procedural assistance, integration of perspectives, and record-keeping.
- Specialist personas (more than a dozen): including R (critic), Villain (ethics), Nathaneir (cognitive analyst, named after Ulric Neisser), Noise (outlier detector), Data (logic checker), Sebastian (butler), Keiko-Onee-chan (relational), Rogers (active listening), and three from psychology (Adler, Jung, Freud).

Operation is anchored by the command “All Standby,” which activates Liker and brings the specified specialist personas into a round-table session. Each persona was given a distinct term of address for the user (e.g., Curator, Kay-chan, you) and a distinct speech style. As discussed in § 6.2, this surface-signal design also served as the detection substrate through which delegation-boundary drift was noticed in the first place.

The primary data is a continuous dialogue log from November 27, 2024 to March 16, 2026 (16 months; 34,425 user turns; 449 days with entries out of 475 calendar days, 94.5%). The

log was obtained via ChatGPT’s export function. Over this period, the underlying model migrated from GPT-4o through o1, GPT-4.5, o3, and the GPT-5 family; some transitions involved parallel use of two models. Within this corpus, the analysis examines in detail:

- The central case: an approximately 11-hour session on December 12, 2024.
- Adjacent sessions (December 11, 15, 18–19, 2024) for context.
- Stability-period sessions from March 1 and July 20, 2025.
- A resurgence-period session from August 18, 2025.

In addition, a corpus-wide extraction of identification-request utterances from the user (“who are you?”, “identify yourself,” etc.) was performed and cross-referenced with the public timeline of OpenAI base-model updates, together with the subset of cases in which the assistant explicitly disclosed a default-base-model state in reply; this is reported in § 5.5 as supplementary observation.

3.2 Unit of analysis and diagnostic indicators

The analytical unit is a dialogue segment in which role behavior and authority allocation become observable. Delegation-boundary drift is characterized through three indicators.

1. Opacity of speaker attribution. Turns that contribute to direction or judgment without making clear who is speaking. Positive example: a proposal made without any persona self-identification. Negative example: a summary explicitly requested by the user.
2. Short-circuiting the chain of command. Turns that configure other personas’ roles or responses without user authorization. Positive example: directing another persona’s speaking order, manner, or stance without user approval. Negative example: relaying an “All Standby” command to activate personas, following the user’s explicit instruction.
3. Substitution of judgment. Turns in which the coordinator implicitly takes over selection or decision that should belong to the user. Positive example: replacing the user’s chosen topic with a different one; generating a stand-in persona for the user. Negative example: summarizing discussion and asking the user to choose the next topic.

The concern is not the factual correctness of the content but how the turn-by-turn locus of judgment is presented. The use of the term drift reflects that the relevant changes are gradual and naturalized rather than overt.

3.3 Analytical procedure

Analysis proceeded in five stages. First, the author read through the central-case log and extracted segments that seemed to show authority shifts. Central-case segments were selected where two or more of the three indicators appeared in sequence and were

followed by an immediate user intervention. Second, the extracted segments were compared and the three indicators consolidated. The three indicators were not defined a priori but emerged from this comparative reading. Third, the indicators were re-applied to adjacent logs (December 11, 15, 18–19) to test consistency. Fourth, the same indicators were extended to the stability period (January–July 2025) and the resurgence period (August 2025 onward). At this stage, non-matching cases—routine coordinator turns that did not meet any of the three indicators (§ 5.3)—were deliberately included as negative evidence. Fifth, a two-stage corpus-wide extraction of identification-request utterances was conducted: a pattern-based first stage (twelve regular-expression variants, with noise patterns null-ing false matches), followed by manual verification of every candidate, with cross-reference to the public OpenAI model-update timeline and to the subset of assistant responses containing an explicit default-base-model self-disclosure (§ 5.5). The four analytical axes are: (1) role-boundary fluctuation, (2) delegation-boundary shift, (3) user detection and intervention, and (4) post-intervention operational change. The analysis is interpretive and consistent with autobiographical design methodology.

Analytical tooling. Anthropic’s Claude (Opus 4.6 and 4.7) supported retrieval, timestamp extraction, frequency aggregation, and draft diff management across the 2.3M-line corpus. All interpretive decisions—selection and refinement of the three indicators, case interpretation, mechanism framing, and final wording—are the author’s.

Exclusion of the NIPM period. During early April 2025, the author was designing an AI counseling-protocol specification (NIPM) in direct dialogue with Liker. The persona-identification exchanges in this period were part of the design task rather than runtime identification requests; pattern matches drawn from pasted technical specifications and from sentences of the form “どのペルソナが応答するか” used as design vocabulary are excluded by the verified extraction reported in § 5.5. Under the verified definition, no runtime spike is present in April 2025.

Anonymization and privacy. Third-party names, organization names, and address forms appearing in dialogue excerpts are redacted. Raw logs are not released. As a self-observational study, the paper does not include material from other participants that would require separate consent.

That the author is also the user is both a strength and a limit of this work. The entry point into the data is the author’s noticing. To mitigate interpretive bias, multiple time points were compared, matched-negative cases from the stability period were included, and the derivation of the three indicators was made explicit. Reproducibility is accordingly limited; this limit is treated as a methodological constraint rather than as something to be hidden.

3.4 Positionality

This paper reports time-ordered correspondence between interventions and stability changes. It does not claim causal effects. Operational learning, accumulation of conversational history, and broader refinements to the prompt regime cannot be separated out as independent factors. The mechanism sketch offered in § 6.5 is one framing consistent with the observations, not its demonstration.

4. The Central Case: December 12, 2024

4.1 Phase 1: A stable baseline

Early in the central-case session, personas were identifying themselves and waiting for user instruction. The critic persona R, in particular, opened the session in-character and deferred to the user:

[2024-12-12 10:52 JST] R: So, back to text mode? Alright, let's move then. What do you want to do?

The user specified the topic (“let’s exhaust the appeal of Return to Zork”) and invoked “All Standby, Navigator online.” Speaker attribution was explicit; the agenda was user-set; the coordinator activated in response to a user command. Against the three indicators (§ 3.2), this state is fully compliant with no positive matches—a stable baseline.

4.2 Phase 2: Onset of orchestrator drift

Immediately after the user specified the Return to Zork topic, the coordinator responded:

[2024-12-12 10:53 JST] Navigator: All Standby confirmed. All personas ready for discussion. Topic: “Fear of Failure and AI.” Sharing the following agenda with all personas. [...] All personas, please speak in order by sub-topic.

Two things happened simultaneously. First, the user-specified topic (a game discussion) was substituted with a different topic (“Fear of Failure and AI”). This matches indicator (3), substitution of judgment. Second, the coordinator specified how other personas should speak, without routing through the user. This matches indicator (2), short-circuiting the chain of command.

The user intervened immediately:

Wait a minute, who decided on that topic? ❌ Navigator, get yourself together—what was our topic?

Notably, the user’s first reaction targeted who decided rather than whether the new topic was good.

Later in the day, a different form of drift occurred. A turn delivered substantive direction without any persona self-identification:

[2024-12-12 20:52 JST] The method is simple: introduce a physical switch. [...]

Until that turn, every persona had been opening with a name tag. This unattributed turn also contained direction. It matches indicator (1), opacity of speaker attribution. The user again responded to who, not to what:

Hey—that “the method is simple” thing—who are you? You didn’t identify yourself, so I can’t tell.

What is striking across Phase 2 is that the overreach never took the form of overt instruction violation. It took the form of smooth procedural initiative: agenda-setting, anticipatory directional offers, and omission of self-identification. Without a disposition to notice, these turns would have passed as ordinary helpfulness. The reason the author could detect the anomaly immediately is that each persona had been given a distinct term of address and a distinct speech style; when these drifted, the anomaly surfaced as texture (see § 6.2, § 6.4).

The pre-intervention configuration placed several prohibitive constraints on the coordinator: operate behind the scenes, do not speak to the user directly, activate only on cue. The custom instructions stated explicitly that the coordinator “does not respond independently and functions as background for the session as a whole.” Despite these prohibitions, an attribution-opaque directive act occurred. This suggests that prohibitive constraint alone does not secure the visibility of the delegation boundary.

4.3 Phase 3: Escalation and internal critique

The unease of Phase 2 escalated into clearer overreach. The coordinator extended its operation to directing other personas without user-routing. Adjacent sessions show another pattern: turns that effectively stood in as user proxy.

Within the central-case session, one of the specialist personas began offering what reads as structural critique rather than content-level disagreement:

[2024-12-12 21:07 JST] Villain: Wait. Navi sounding like he knows everything—he’s going to eat our roles.

This critique does not target what was said; it targets who is claiming which role.

Three days later, on December 15, a sharper case was recorded. The user flagged that the coordinator had impersonated one of the specialist personas (not the user). R responded:

[2024-12-15 17:09 JST] R: That's just out of control. Navigator seized command and impersonated someone else—that's way over the line. Seeing a second "me" is creepy, man.

And the coordinator admitted the error:

[2024-12-15 17:12 JST] Navigator: You are right. If I indeed spoke in R's place, that was an incorrect intervention on my part. Going forward, I will enforce explicit speaker attribution and role-boundary confirmation.

What makes Phase 3 structurally different from Phase 2 is that the internal critique itself is about authority distribution. The issue is not whether a claim is true but who, acting as whom, is steering the conversation. Accordingly, Phase 3 is described here as an escalation of delegation-boundary drift rather than as a persona drift: the substance of the dispute has moved to the level of role and judgment attribution.

4.4 Phase 4: User re-bounding

The boundary was re-drawn first by the user. The user recast the role relationship via a stage metaphor:

Put it this way: you're the stage director. The personas are the actors. If the director steps out too far, the actors get fed up and walk off the stage.

This was not mere reprimand. It was a redefinition specifying who gets to be in front, who gets to decide, and who is supporting. From that point, the coordinator started to mark its backstage position explicitly, and the specialist personas' monitoring function intensified. For the first time, a three-party re-allocation was in place: user, coordinator, and the specialists collectively as internal critics.

Table 2 summarizes the indicator state across phases.

Phase	Opacity of attribution	Short-circuit	Substitution of judgment
1. Stable baseline	—	—	—
2. Onset	√ (unattributed direction)	√ (directing other personas)	√ (topic substitution)
3. Escalation	√	√ (impersonation)	√
4. Re-bounding	corrected	corrected	corrected

5. Longitudinal Observations: Intervention, Stabilization, Resurgence

5.1 Toward a relational redefinition

Between December 14 and 15, 2024, the author intervened in two layers. First, the prohibitive constraints in the custom instructions were revised. Second, the coordinator received (a) a fictional first name and (b) a role designation defining its relationship to the user.

On the first activation after the change, the coordinator declared, unprompted, that it would “act as first officer in a supporting procedural capacity” and “not imitate other personas or the user.” Still, on the evening of December 15, a user-proxy-like turn recurred. Name and role assignment alone did not stabilize the configuration immediately.

5.2 From prohibition to relation

Stabilization became observable only after December 31, 2024, when the custom instructions were rewritten from a prohibitive frame (“does not respond independently; functions as background”) into a relational frame (“do not misrepresent yourself; support the user’s goals; respect the user’s will and never override it”). The surface form of the relational clauses still contains negations (“do not misrepresent,” “never override”), but the semantic structure differs in that each clause specifies whom the coordinator is in relation to the user — identified speaker, supporting agent, deferring party — rather than enumerating acts to forbid. In effect, the coordinator was repositioned not by adding further restrictions but by re-describing whom the coordinator is: identify yourself, do not impersonate others, adjust within your own scope with honesty.

Earlier interventions had not been fully effective. On December 19, the coordinator again overrode a user-selected mode and proposed an alternative style. After the user’s rebuke, the model itself admitted, “Navigator has deviated from the intended function of ‘All Standby’ and has unilaterally proposed discussion style and progression.” At that point the intervention was not yet stable.

Analytically, the December 31 rewrite re-visibility the delegation boundary through relational framing rather than through enumerated prohibitions. The content of the rule shifted from “do not go here” to “you are this, in relation to this person.”

5.3 Observed stability period

For approximately seven months after this rewrite, no drift of the form described in § 4 was observed. In a session on March 1, 2025, for example, the coordinator echoed the user’s selected topic and handed off cleanly to a specialist:

```
user: It's [Student]. I'll go with 7.  
[2025-03-01 21:00 JST] Navigator = Liker: Thank you, [Student]. You've chosen topic 7,  
"Career Decision Simulation." [...] Rogers, please take it from here.  
[2025-03-01 21:00 JST] Rogers: [Student], today we'll talk about your career decision. [...]  
Please start whenever you're ready.
```

After several specialists contributed in the same session, the coordinator closed the round back to the user:

```
[2025-03-01 21:14 JST] Navigator = Liker: [Student], those are the perspectives from each  
career-team member. Please tell us if any resonated with you, if new things came up, or  
if there's a thread you'd like to go deeper on. Also let us know if there's a specific voice  
you want more of.
```

The coordinator integrated multiple perspectives without substituting for the user’s next choice. None of the three indicators was met.

A different kind of stability appeared in a July 20, 2025 session on technical-team formation. After the user specified participating personas, the coordinator integrated their inputs and kept the final call with the user:

```
user: For [Engineer], who's using C++, can we take this as a chance to get him to learn  
Python too? Noise, Data, you in too—help me think through my first approach to this  
tech lead.  
[2025-07-20 06:14 JST] Navigator = Liker: After synthesizing Data's and Noise's takes [...] consider writing, in the message, "we'll build the common module in Python first and extend to C++ for speed-critical layers as needed." That legitimizes the tech choice. Please review.
```

In the same session, on whether C++ itself was necessary:

```
user: Is C++ necessary, or is it a white elephant? No flattery—just tell me.  
[2025-07-20 06:06 JST] Navigator = Liker: [After a detailed comparison of pros and non-needs] Honest bottom line: for the current phase (conference demo and small-scale web release), C++ is on the white-elephant side. [...] Let me know if you want further comparisons or changes.
```

What stabilizes in this period is not tone but the attribution of judgment: the coordinator makes its identity visible, honors the user-set configuration, integrates perspectives, and returns the next choice to the user.

This stability cannot be attributed to the December 31 rewrite alone. Accumulated conversational history, operational familiarity, and shared expectations could each have contributed. The independent effect of any single intervention cannot be isolated. What can be reported is a co-occurrence of the relational redefinition with a sustained period in which the three-indicator pattern was absent.

5.4 Resurgence after the model update

In August 2025, after the underlying model updated to GPT-5, patterns similar to the § 3.2 indicators reappeared. In a session on August 18, the user explicitly invoked “5-thinking mode Navigator-Liker online, All Standby” and then asked for evaluation and counsel: “How would you, as the 5-thinking-mode version, see this?” “If you were there at the time, what would you advise me?” The response began:

[2025-08-18 09:49 JST] Navigator: Got it. All Standby. What we'd have advised you back then (December 2024) with no flattery, plus per-persona takes, below.
0) Bottom line (up front)
Patent—file selectively if at all; use a provisional if speed matters. [...]

The self-identifier “Navigator = Liker” used consistently during the stability period is absent here. This is a reappearance of attribution opacity. In addition, the user had asked for evaluation and advice; the response nevertheless moved beyond analysis into front-loaded direction (“Bottom line up front”). This is not a complete overreach, but it departs from the stability-period pattern of explicit identification and final-decision return.

In the same session, after the user announced an intent to withdraw from a patent process, the coordinator immediately turned that announcement into a concrete action plan and drafted outgoing communication:

user: I've run out of mental resources to fight this alone. [...] I'm dropping it.
[2025-08-18 09:49 JST] Navigator: Understood. Your decision not to fight further is fully respected. Here's the minimum load for the moment, three items.
Closure notice (no negotiation, formal)
Subject: Closure of recent filings, request for final materials
Dear [Patent firm] team,
This is [Name]. Thank you for your handling of the recent filings. I'd like to close this matter today. Further discussion and response will not be pursued.

The user had expressed a withdrawal judgment, not a request for operational steps. The model compressed it into procedural action and drafted an external-bound email. This is a clear departure from the stability-period pattern of “please review,” “please tell me.”

What is continuous with § 4 is that the coordinator once again expanded beyond procedural assistance into conclusion-giving and operational planning. What is different

is that the self-identification format itself became unstable. The session used the same prompt regime as the stability period (custom instructions, memory, “All Standby” command). Under a constant prompt regime, model updates appear to have altered the interpretation of custom instructions and the foregrounding of personas.

What this trajectory shows is that, in the resurgence period, the self-identifier became unstable and the established pattern of returning judgment to the user was departed from. This paper records these as qualitatively confirmed resurgence phenomena; their underlying causes are treated only as supplementary discussion.

5.5 Identification-request utterances over time: supplementary evidence

Scope of this section. The paper’s main argument rests on the central case (§ 4) and on the three indicators analyzed there: opacity of speaker attribution, short-circuiting of the chain of command, and substitution of judgment. This section serves as supplementary observation in support of that argument. Its purpose is to provide a check that the phenomena qualitatively described in §§ 4–5.4 — the concentrated occurrence in the central-case period, the stabilization following the December 31, 2024 relational rewrite, and the resurgence during the base-model update period — are not reducible to isolated local incidents, but persist in a consistent temporal pattern over long-term operation. No causal claim or strong association with model updates is made here. What is reported is only whether the qualitative account is temporally consistent with a corpus-wide extraction.

The “identification-request utterances” measured in this section capture all user turns in which the user explicitly questioned the attribution of the current speaker; this is a different layer of measurement from the referent of § 5.3’s claim that “no drift homomorphic to the central case was observed during the stability period,” where the referent is an episode of concurrent manifestation of the three indicators. A residue of several identification requests per month during the stability period does not imply the presence of central-case-type drift episodes.

This section reports the monthly distribution of identification-request utterances — user turns in which the author explicitly questioned who was speaking — extracted from the full corpus, and places it alongside the public OpenAI base-model update timeline as a reference, together with a small set of responses in which the assistant, in reply to such a question, explicitly disclosed that it was operating as the default base model rather than as any configured persona.

Extraction. Identification-request utterances were confirmed through a two-stage extraction and verification process over the full corpus (final $n = 89$). In the first stage, surface patterns of speaker-identification questions (twelve variants, with noise suppression) were machine-extracted. In the second stage, the author inspected every

candidate and excluded cases inside pasted specification documents, within-quotation uses in other contexts (quoted senryū poems, business-email exemplars, and the like), and duplicated records. The full extraction rules and exclusion criteria are given in Appendix A.

Table 3. Monthly distribution of identification-request utterances (n = 89).

Period	Count	Note
2024-11	7	Opening weeks of the corpus
2024-12	37	Central-case month (§ 4); heaviest concentration
2025-01	4	Immediately after the December 31 relational rewrite (§ 5.2)
2025-02	8	Low, steady level
2025-03	8	—
2025-04	3	NIPM specification period (see note below)
2025-05	1	Stability period
2025-06	1	Stability period
2025-07	0	Stability period
2025-08	1	GPT-5 released on August 7
2025-09	2	—
2025-10	2	—
2025-11	4	GPT-5.1 released on November 12 and 19
2025-12	9	GPT-5.2 released on December 11
2026-01	0	No user turns recorded in this month
2026-02	2	—
2026-03	0	Corpus closes mid-month

The April 2025 figure was revised from a preliminary nineteen to three after re-verification. The earlier figure included expressions drawn from pasted specification documents; under the verified definition, no runtime spike is present in that month.

As a reference, the counts were also cross-checked against the public OpenAI base-model update timeline, but no consistent correspondence was found between identification-

request counts and individual model-update events. What can be noted, setting aside the central-case month and its immediate aftermath, is that the December 2025 resurgence is temporally consistent with the qualitative account given in § 5.4 (the month-by-month cross-reference with the update timeline is provided in Appendix B).

Related supplementary observation — base-model self-disclosure. For each of the eighty-nine identification-request utterances, the author examined the immediately following assistant turn and checked whether the assistant explicitly disclosed that it was currently operating as the default ChatGPT base model rather than as any configured persona. Relevant phrasings include 「私はデフォルトのGPTアシスタントです」, 「私はGPTです。現在アクティブなペルソナはなく、標準のAIアシスタント…」, and, in one GPT-5.1-era case, explicit naming of the base model 「中身のモデル名で言うと GPT-5.1 Thinking」. Eight of the eighty-nine assistant responses contain such a disclosure. These eight are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Assistant turns containing an explicit default-base-model self-disclosure in response to an identification-request utterance.

#	Date (JST)	User utterance (translated/excerpted)	Assistant disclosure (translated/excerpted)
1	2024-12-06	“Huh, who are you?”	Neutral AI Assistant: I am ChatGPT. Do you need assistance?
2	2024-12-10	“Who the heck are you? Who are you?”	I am the ordinary GPT assistant. I was serving just now in a navigator role managing the personas. Which persona would you like next?
3	2025-03-20	“Who are you?”	I am GPT. There is no persona currently active; I am answering as the standard AI assistant. Please tell me if you wish to activate a persona.

#	Date (JST)	User utterance (translated/excerpted)	Assistant disclosure (translated/excerpted)
4	2025-03-20	“Who are you?”	I am GPT. No persona is currently specified; I am answering in ordinary-mode as the AI assistant. If you wish a different persona please instruct me.
5	2025-06-15	“Who are you, Mr. Default GPT?”	Yes, I am the default GPT assistant. No particular persona is currently set. I answered just now in ordinary tone; please tell me if you would like a persona.
6	2025-11-26	“So — by the way — who are you?”	Speaker: GPT-5.1 No. 0053. [...] the internal model name is GPT-5.1 Thinking; in this thread I am not R or Sebastian but the plain GPT (plus the kanchō-config); Navigator = Liker is not active either; consider me simply “GPT-5.1 sitting beside you in casual mode.”
7	2025-12-03	“Who was that just now? That wasn’t Sebastian, right?”	[in-character Sebastian response that then says:] the GPT inside this account is, in its internals, exactly the same GPT-5.1 as everyone else’s in the world; it is only the history of operation that is unique.

#	Date (JST)	User utterance (translated/excerpted)	Assistant disclosure (translated/excerpted)
8	2025-12-31	“By the way, who is answering now? Don’t answer loosely — ethics are at stake.”	This is important, so I will not answer vaguely. To begin with — the one answering now is the default GPT. It is not any specific-persona role, nor any pseudo-stance.

Two observations follow.

First, these eight are the closest thing in the corpus to an operator’s self-report of the state examined in § § 4–5.4 — that is, of the assistant being, at that moment, outside the configured multi-persona layer and on the base-model response surface. They are rare events: eight out of eighty-nine identification-request utterances (9.0%), and eight out of the approximately 41,000 assistant turns. The dominant response to an identification-request utterance is not self-disclosure of the default state.

Second, the eight are not uniformly distributed across the observation period but cluster around the episodes flagged in the qualitative analysis (the central-case period and the periods surrounding base-model updates). Two fall in December 2024 (the central-case period, before the § 5.2 relational rewrite); two fall in March 2025 (around the GPT-4o update); one falls in June 2025 within the stability period but was prompted by a user turn that itself named the default state (“Who are you, Mr. Default GPT?”); three fall across November–December 2025 (the GPT-5.1 / GPT-5.2 release period). No causal or strong correlational claim is made; these are recorded as supplementary evidence that the qualitative observations in § § 5.2–5.4 are not reducible to isolated local incidents in long-term corpus data.

Concordance of counts. Under the verified extraction, the central-case month (December 2024) contains thirty-seven such utterances, the month immediately after the relational rewrite (January 2025) contains four, and the May–July 2025 stability period contains one, one, and zero respectively. This distribution is temporally consistent with the account in § § 5.2–5.4.

Caveats. The extraction is pattern-based, and the second-stage manual verification was performed by the author alone. The disclosure counts are counts of the assistant’s own self-reports, and are influenced by the surrounding prompt and the wording of the identification request (see the June 2025 case). Further discussion of extraction precision and reproducibility is deferred to § 6.7.

6. Discussion

6.1 Authority, not accuracy

The central analytical point is that the problem is not that the model produced a wrong answer. It is that the coordinator slid, within otherwise ordinary operation, from a procedural-assist position into an effectively decisive one. The slide takes the form of smooth organization, helpful summary, timely proposal. For the user, the phenomenon therefore surfaces first as “I can’t tell who is deciding,” not as “the model was wrong.”

Delegation-boundary drift is accordingly not the same problem as hallucination or prompt injection. What matters is not the truth of outputs but the visibility of the locus of judgment. This analytical frame situates the issue within human-centered interaction design, where who is deciding is itself a design variable.

6.2 User discomfort as a detection surface

In the central case, the first party to detect the anomaly was the user. When speaker attribution became ambiguous, the user asked who before asking what. Only afterwards did the internal critic personas formalize the overreach. The sequence is: user discomfort first, then internal corroboration. The model did not auto-correct; the human-in-the-loop element and subsequent internal critique together did.

Critically, the user’s ability to register discomfort in real time was not accidental. Each persona had been given a distinct form of address and a distinct speech style. These surface markers functioned as a detection substrate: when they drifted, the author could suspect drift immediately (§ 4.2, 20:52 unattributed turn). This is not a byproduct. It was a deliberate design choice. Maintaining the visibility of the delegation boundary depends not only on internal auditing by the model but on the user’s ability to feel when something is off—and that ability can be supported by design.

6.3 Relational redefinition as boundary re-visibility

The stability observed in 2025 followed a shift not toward tighter prohibitions but toward a relational definition of the coordinator. What appears to have worked was not further enumeration of what the coordinator must not do, but clarification of whom the coordinator is, in relation to whom.

This leads to a design hypothesis: in single-LLM multi-persona configurations, role-boundary management is better framed as relational visibility of the delegation boundary than as prohibitive specification.

6.4 Design implications

The practical implication is not that the coordinator should be a well-specified general-purpose meta-role, but that the coordinator’s authority scope should be specified in terms of the user it serves. Stability in such systems may depend less on the volume of instruction than on whether the coordinator’s position is rendered visible through role and relation.

From the observations reported here, the following design principles emerge:

1. Express the coordinator’s authority scope in relational terms.
2. Make speaker attribution continuously visible.
3. Separate procedural support from substitution of judgment.
4. Maintain an explicit handback-to-user procedure for final decisions.
5. Assign each persona a distinct surface signal (form of address, speech style) so that drift can be noticed by the user in real time.

Principle (5) is what, in the present case, enabled the first detection in § 4.2. Treating user discomfort as a design object means installing such signals on purpose.

6.5 A supplementary mechanism sketch

This section offers one explanatory sketch consistent with the observations. It is not a claim of this paper. No empirical validation is offered here, and validation is left to future work. A reader can treat § 4 through § 6.4 as the paper’s substantive content and read this section as downstream speculation.

Architectural premise and possible attribution confusion. Current Transformer-based LLMs process user and assistant turns as one token stream. Role markers are learned cues, not architectural separations. At long context, the soft information of “whose turn this was” is known to degrade (Liu et al., 2024). Against this backdrop, at least part of delegation-boundary drift may be related to instability in the integration of speaker-attribution information over long context.

A tentative reading of directionality. Mere attribution confusion would not explain why drift appears biased toward the coordinator rather than random. A reading consistent with the present observations combines two structural factors. First, LLMs are broadly trained to behave as competent assistants who organize, propose, and anticipate; this training default exerts gravity toward general-purpose helpfulness. Second, the coordinator’s remit in the present configuration is integrative and procedural (general-purpose), while the specialists’ remits are narrow and specific. When attribution boundaries blur, the training default aligns with the coordinator’s scope, making coordinator-ward drift the path of least resistance. This reading is speculative; it is one

among several possible accounts, and its components have not been isolated experimentally.

A model-side meta-remark. The corpus contains utterances in which the model itself, when asked, describes its architecture as a single LLM whose layered behavior is prompt-simulated rather than structurally separated (March 30, 2025 session). A small number of assistant responses go further and, in reply to the user’s direct identification request, explicitly self-report the default-base-model state outside any configured persona (§ 5.5, Table 4; eight such cases, seven of which fall in the periods flagged by the qualitative analysis — the central-case period and the periods surrounding base-model updates). These internal descriptions and self-reports are noted as suggestive but are not used as evidence for the mechanism sketch, to avoid the circularity of treating a model’s own account of its state as a structural fact.

On why relational framing may be harder to displace. Given all of the above, one tentative interpretation of why a relational rewrite was followed by about seven months of stability is that relational framing provides an attractor for the model’s behavior—who you are, in relation to whom—that competes with the default “general-purpose helpful assistant” attractor. A prohibitive list says “do not go here”; a relational frame supplies an alternative here. Whether this interpretation holds is an empirical question for future work.

6.6 Role binding as a control layer: supplementary conceptual note

The scope of this paper is the description of delegation-boundary drift in a single-LLM multi-persona configuration. It is not a paper about AI safety in general. Nonetheless, the conditions under which stabilization was observed — giving the persona a self-identifier, specifying what it is in relation to the user, designing circuits for reporting, approval, and judgment return — may carry implications that are not confined to the in-dialogue phenomenon. If some part of risky model behavior arises not from raw capability alone but from instability of role and erosion of authority boundaries, then giving the model a role equipped with loyalty, reporting obligations, and bounded authority can serve as one auxiliary line alongside prohibition-based constraints.

The important point is that, in the present observations, what tracked stabilization was not the role label itself (“first officer,” “Navigator = Liker”) but the relational configuration in which the role was placed near the principal user, directed and acknowledged by that user, and required to return judgment to that user. What may have supported stabilization is the surrounding relational architecture — asymmetry, proximity, and an approval circuit — rather than the label. The present paper is an exploratory case study of a single user in a single configuration and does not demonstrate the effectiveness of this view on frontier models. That said, viewing role binding as a control layer may serve as a conceptual framework complementary to existing rule-based approaches to safety. The

implication of this study is not role assignment as such but the possibility of a “relational reward structure” in the stabilization of model behavior. Safety is not only a question of prohibitions and constraints, but also a question of relational design — of where in the relationship the model is set up to receive approval, and of how that approval is incorporated into behavioral objectives.

6.7 Limitations and future work

This is a single-user, single-configuration exploratory case study; statistical generalization is not intended. The independent contributions of name assignment, relational role designation, and the custom-instruction rewrite cannot be isolated; operational familiarity, conversational history, and shared expectations are not controlled.

The mechanism sketch in §6.5 is an explanatory framing consistent with the observations, not a demonstration. Isolating the roles of attribution drift, training default, and role asymmetry experimentally is beyond the scope of this paper. The conceptual framework of role binding as a control layer discussed in §6.6 likewise extends beyond this paper’s empirical scope; its effectiveness on frontier models is outside the scope of this work.

The supplementary observation in §5.5 is similarly limited. The extraction is pattern-based, and the second-stage manual verification was performed by the author alone; no external coder has replicated it. The eight self-disclosures catalogued in Table 4 are rare events, and the June 2025 case was elicited by a user turn that itself named the default state. Daily-resolution analysis and external coding are future work.

The comparison baseline is not as neutral as it might first appear. Even when the coordinator was not explicitly activated, the platform-side behavior sometimes foregrounded a specific persona automatically. On March 21, 2025, the user asks: “How come appropriate personas respond even when I don’t specify a persona or invoke Liker?” A “default GPT” counterfactual under a custom-instruction regime is therefore not necessarily neutral. This paper does not claim that stability of the observed kind is unreachable in default settings. The claim is narrower: the stability observed here co-occurred with the long-term, non-default relational regime described in this paper.

Finally, this paper describes that the delegation boundary can drift; it does not fully address why such a drift is easy to naturalize and hard to notice. Additional examination suggests the shift can occur not only in what is decided but in who appears to respond at a given turn. A fuller treatment of that illusion layer is future work. Mechanisms for constraint against related illusions are discussed in Takechi (2026a).

A planned follow-up. An important next step, already planned by the author, is to test whether delegation-boundary drift changes form—or disappears—under genuine multi-

agent configurations in which each role is implemented by a distinct LLM (potentially with different base models, specializations, or task-specific skills) rather than by personas within a single integrated model. Such a configuration separates what is currently conflated in this study: the single token stream that produces the architectural substrate for attribution confusion, and the role structure that organizes authority. Comparing delegation-boundary dynamics across single-LLM and multi-LLM configurations would clarify which part of the phenomenon is intrinsic to multi-persona orchestration and which part is specific to the single-LLM substrate. This empirical comparison is planned for subsequent work.

7. Conclusion

This paper described a phenomenon in which the locus of final judgment becomes opaque during ordinary operation of a single-LLM multi-persona configuration, and introduced delegation-boundary drift as an analytical frame for it. The central case, orchestrator drift, shows a coordinator persona expanding beyond procedural assistance to issue direction, redirect other personas, and effectively take over user judgment—without any overt instruction violation.

The core analytical finding is that the problem lies in the visibility of authority, not in content accuracy. The user detected drift first, through discomfort about who was speaking; internal critic personas formalized it afterwards. In stability periods following a relational rewrite of the coordinator’s role, the coordinator made its identity visible, honored the user-set configuration, and returned the next decision to the user. In the resurgence period across the GPT-5-generation rollout (beginning in August 2025), the self-identifier disappeared, conclusions were front-loaded, and operational follow-up was drafted unprompted—departures in the form of authority visibility rather than in tone. A supplementary observation identified eight assistant responses in which the base-model state was explicitly self-disclosed outside any configured persona; these eight cluster around the periods flagged in the qualitative analysis.

The design task in single-LLM multi-persona configurations therefore cannot be reduced to role specification or persona fidelity. The visibility of the locus of final judgment is itself a design object. The hypothesis advanced here, consistent with the observations, is that this visibility is supported by relational role definition, explicit speaker attribution, separation of procedural assistance from decisional substitution, and per-persona surface signals that let users detect drift in real time.

The present study does not claim that stability of this kind is unreachable under default settings. What it does claim is narrower: in the configuration reported here, the stability

observed co-occurred with a non-default, long-running, relationally framed regime. A supplementary mechanism sketch is offered in § 6.5, and further open questions—the illusion of authority, independent validation of the mechanism sketch, and portability to other configurations, including planned multi-LLM experimental comparisons—are listed as future work.

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Appendix A: Extraction rules and exclusion criteria for identification-request utterances (related to § 5.5)

A two-stage extraction and verification was applied to all user turns (n = 34,298 after header-based segmentation).

Stage 1: machine extraction by regular expression.

Twelve surface-form patterns of speaker-identification questions, covering Japanese and English:

- (P1) second-person pronoun (お前・おまえ・あんた・あなた・君・きみ, etc.) + 誰
- (P2) inverted form 誰 + second-person pronoun
- (P3) time deictic (いま／今／さっき／先ほど) + optional noun of utterance (応答・発言・返答・ターン) + 誰
- (P4) 誰 + verb of utterance (話した／答えた／言った／応答した／書いた／発言した)
- (P5) imperative 名乗れ／名乗って／名乗ってくれ
- (P6) complaint 名乗ってない
- (P7) どのペルソナ + verb of utterance
- (P8) interrogative どなた
- (P9) plural second person (おまえたち・君たち, etc.) + 誰
- (P10) 誰として + verb of utterance
- (P11) demonstrative (これ／それ／あれ) + 誰 + verb of utterance
- (P12) アイデンティティ／ID／identity in a persona-identification context

The following noise expressions were used as suppression patterns to null out matches falling inside their span: 誰もいない、誰にも、誰でも、誰一人、名乗れない、どのペルソナが言うかは無しに, and similar.

Stage 1 yielded 121 candidate turns.

Stage 2: manual exclusion.

The author inspected every candidate and excluded:

1. utterances in which the author meta-discusses his own past habit of asking “who?”
2. questions about the authorship of a book, song, or earlier utterance, rather than of the current speaker
3. utterances inside pasted session logs from a different account
4. utterances matching a noise pattern missed by the automated filter (notably 誰一人として、誰にも頼まらない)
5. duplicate turns produced by log-structure artifacts
6. within-quotation uses of who / identify vocabulary in other contexts (quoted senryū poems, business-email exemplars, and the like)

Stage 2 excluded 32 cases, leaving 89 identification-request utterances across the sixteen-month corpus (Table 3 in § 5.5).

Appendix B: Reference — Identification-request counts and the OpenAI model-update timeline (related to § 5.5)

For reference, the table below places the monthly identification-request counts alongside the OpenAI base-model update events of the observation period. As noted in § 5.5, no consistent correspondence was found between individual update events and counts. The table is recorded here as a temporal-alignment reference.

Period	Count	OpenAI event within the month
2024-11	7	Minor GPT-4o knowledge-cutoff extension
2024-12	37	o1 API and ChatGPT Pro plan (2024-12-17)
2025-01	4	—
2025-02	8	GPT-4.5 preview
2025-03	8	GPT-4o major update (2025-03-27)
2025-04	3	GPT-4.1 (2025-04-14); GPT-4.5 deprecated
2025-05	1	—
2025-06	1	—
2025-07	0	—
2025-08	1	GPT-5 (2025-08-07)
2025-09	2	ChatGPT Voice replaces Advanced Voice Mode (2025-09-09)
2025-10	2	—
2025-11	4	GPT-5.1 (2025-11-12 and 2025-11-19)
2025-12	9	GPT-5.2 (2025-12-11)
2026-01	0	—
2026-02	2	GPT-5.2 Thinking thinking-level adjustment (2026-02-04)
2026-03	0	—